

EN1317: A standard out of date?

Wolf P Zeplin and **José F Papí** believe that it may be time for an update... before it's too late

The EN 1317 European standard was developed within the framework of the Construction Products Directive 89/106/EEC and EN1317-5 serves as a basis for the CE marking of road safety systems such as safety barriers and guardrails, crash cushions, barrier extremities and transitions. The release of EN1317 – after years of research, testing and standardisation efforts – represented a major step ahead for addressing at least 30-40 per cent of road fatalities, which are associated with single-vehicle collisions.

The authors are of the opinion that today a number of challenges that might affect the reliability of the existing EN standards are on the table:

High-performance steel barriers: have they been sufficiently tested for impacts with SUVs and larger passenger vehicles?

Challenge 1: Have Vehicle Restraint Systems (VRS) adapted themselves to the new generation of vehicles?

Crash tests use models of cars, trucks and buses with pre-defined weights and dimensions as standard parameters for the tests.

For instance, tests according to TB 11 use small cars weighing about 1,100kg. At the same time, a new category of vehicles with higher centres of gravity and higher chassis altitude, the so-called Sport Utility Vehicles (SUVs), are gaining acceptance in the market (from 6.5 per cent in 2006 to 18 per cent in 2014). SUVs weigh from 1,500 to 3,500kg, with average horsepower having increased from 95 HP in 1995 to 140 HP in 2014.

Does a barrier tested according to TB 11 contain SUVs effectively? Since the maximum car weight in TB 32 is

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Testing must cover wider groups of vehicles to ensure across-the-board safety

1,500kg, and the next level is TB 41 with 10,000kg, it seems that no crash-test caters for safe SUV containment.

Research has shown that SUV collisions result in serious injuries, especially when ‘regular’ passenger cars are involved, due to the heavier mass and volume, plus the higher chassis structure of the SUV. In addition, the analysis of 955 impact cases with steel and concrete RRS showed an eight-times higher risk for SUV rollover compared to normal pickups and passenger cars.

Similar lines of thought might be opened in relation to other vehicle categories:

- o Can buses (urban use) and coaches (interurban use) be assimilated in crash-tests?
- o Is TB 81 adapted to the new generation of mega-trucks, with weights up to 60,000kg?

In short, the characterization of vehicles used in crash tests according to EN 1317 does not seem restrictive enough, as it allows the testing, for the same technical class, of different

types of vehicles whose performance under impact might differ and, subsequently, determine the obtaining of quite different results.

Challenge 2: Are road authorities aware of the risks posed to private and commercial drivers by the lack of consistent EU practices when it comes to road safety, especially in the context of international road trips?

EU official declarations and several accompanying funding programmes call for the realisation of an ambitious Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T) amounting up to 136,706km of roads by 2030. However, this political impulse has not been accompanied by any technical harmonisation across the TEN-T network as a whole, or across the so-called TEN-T Corridors in particular.

The EU is stressing the importance of optimising the use of infrastructure along the TEN-T Corridors, “notably through intelligent transport systems, efficient management and the promotion of future-oriented clean transport solutions”¹, but little is said about the role of road equipment when it comes to a more efficient and safer network management.

In short, drivers crossing Europe will find totally diverse containment levels and signalling practices for the same type of hazardous spots, therefore making trans-national trips a dangerous activity for the average driver.

This challenge has been even exacerbated by recent proposals in the UK and Germany calling for the relinquishment of the European harmonization process that led to the adoption of EN1317. Such calls might have an effect on the credibility of the European norm, not only within Europe but also in the context of global competition with other international VRS-related standards.

Challenge 3: Does EN1317 cover all possible critical issues involving an VRS?

For instance, today no test or certification is available for barrier connections and junctions of different containment levels (such as N2 to H1 or H1 to H2); the same lack applies to the connection of double beam systems to triple beam systems, of RAL systems to NH systems.

Another example: no tests are made above 100km/h, and therefore the consequences of a crash at 130km/h on a motorway have not been studied in detail.

REFERENCE

¹ Information retrieved from http://ec.europa.eu/transport/themes/infrastructure/news/2015-01-15-corridors_en.htm

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Challenge 4: Do the existing ‘severity indexes’ express accurately the severity of the impact on the occupants of a vehicle involved in an impact against an RRS?

Research and day-to-day practice have highlighted a lack of correlation between the various ‘severity indexes’ available. ASI (acceleration severity index), THIV (theoretical head impact velocity) and PHD (post-impact head deceleration) were chosen two decades years ago. Each of them had been in use for a long time in one or several European countries, as they represented the state-of-the-art in those countries at the time.

In addition, the working towards the elaboration of EN1317 pointed out that the co-existence of three different indexes should be only provisional and the need for a comprehensive revision of the ASI/THIV/PHD Severity Indices based on the results of on-going scientific research and taking into account bio-mechanical and vehicle deformation (VCDI)-related data.

Challenge 5: Why is there a lack of accuracy and reliability in the measurements emerging from test-houses?

The differences in test results can be attributed to a series of factors, listed below into two categories:

1. Factors related to the standard itself:
 - o The choice of the type of vehicle, which is not exactly the same in all test-houses (EN 1317 only specifies the geometric and mass characteristics of the vehicle),
 - o The ground conditions, which have not been precisely defined in the standard,
 - o The choice of the critical impact point,
 - o The location of the acceleration-measuring device,

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- o Control of installation works,
- o Attestation of material evaluation.

2. Factors related to the practices the test-houses:
 - o The type of electronic system used for the recording and computing of test data,
 - o The exact conditions and procedures of the measuring operations,
 - o All other relevant conditions associated with the crash-test, such as the state of the road surface, its skid resistance, etc.

While the factors listed first fall under the responsibility of the trans-national harmonisation dialogue held in the framework of CEN, it is up to test-houses and to notified bodies to deal with the second set of factors, and therefore to reduce all uncertainties related to test measurements.

In any case, at the end of the day cooperative efforts in this matter are lacking, and test-houses run tests in very diverse conditions. In addition, there is not a consensus on the maximum acceptable rate of uncertainty for each kind of measurement.

THE WAY AHEAD

Taking into consideration the challenges described above (which do not constitute an exhaustive list), the authors call for a renewed dialogue between road agencies, standardisation bodies, test-houses and industry to adapt EN 1317 to today’s traffic and the requirements of a harmonised Trans-European Transport Network. In our opinion, the alternative (inaction) is no longer acceptable.

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